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THE INFLUENCE OF SAGITTAL MALOCCLUSION ON NASAL BREATHING DISORDERS

Abstract.

The main etiological factor in the formation of narrowing of the dental arches is a violation of the respiratory function and, as a consequence, an acquired bad habit - breathing through the mouth. The root causes that provoke the appearance of mouth breathing: hypertrophy of the adenoids and tonsils, rhinitis, curvature of the nasal septum, foreign bodies, nasal polyposis. The development of the upper respiratory tract and the facial skeleton are closely interconnected: mouth breathing leads to growth retardation and narrowing of the maxillary sinuses and upper jaw, which causes the formation of the Gothic shape of the palate. The etiopathogenetic mechanism for the development of narrowing of the dental arches is very diverse, but there is insufficient information on the relationship between narrowed dental arches and nasal cavities that determine changes in the facial skull.

Key words: nasal breathing disorder, mouth breathing, narrowing of the upper jaw, sagittal malocclusion

The prevalence of dentoalveolar anomalies and malocclusions among children, according to many authors, continues to be quite high – from 35–75% [1, 2, 3, 4]. Among them, sagittal malocclusions prevail, their prevalence, according to various sources, ranges from 33 to 67% [5]. A number of factors, both endogenous and exogenous, influence the process of formation of the child's dentoalveolar apparatus. Endogenous factors include: genetic predisposition, intrauterine developmental disorders, congenital anomalies, diseases of young children, endocrine pathology. Exogenous factors include: violation of the rules of artificial feeding and dysfunction of the dentoalveolar apparatus (chewing, swallowing, breathing, speech) – bad habits, injuries, previous inflammatory processes in soft and hard tissues, violation of the timing of tooth replacement and their premature removal.

From early sources it is known that the first person to study the problem of upper airway obstruction was Mayer, who in 1869 described patients who adapted to mouth breathing and clinically had a more nasal voice, open mouth and swollen lips [6]. In 1872, Tomes first introduced the term "adenoid face" and suggested that the cause was enlarged adenoids [7]. Tomes's work was widely supported by many orthodontists around the world, and in 1939 Todd and Broadbent introduced the term "long face syndrome" into orthodontics. In 1907, Angel described airway obstruction as an important etiological factor in occlusion pathology [8]. The mechanisms of occurrence of anomalies in children with impaired nasal breathing were also studied by M.M. Vankevich (1929), who discovered that during oral breathing the myodynamic balance of antagonist and synergist muscles changes. When the pharyngeal tonsil is enlarged, children throw their heads back, especially to the right, and thereby shift the lower jaw back. Such a position of the lower jaw over a long period of time

can lead to the appearance of a prognathic (distal) bite. With hypertrophy of the lingual tonsil, the passage of air from the nasal cavity is complicated. To facilitate breathing, during the day the child protrudes the tongue, and during sleep his lower jaw takes a mesial position. As a result of the displacement of the tongue from the epiglottis, conditions are created for facilitating the passage of the air stream and a prognathic (mesial) bite is gradually formed. The position of the tongue also changes, the activity of the masticatory and buccal muscles increases, which leads to the formation of incisor disocclusion [9]. Betelman A.I. (1965) explains the occurrence of sagittal bite anomalies by a number of etiological factors and identifies three main ones: genetic, congenital and acquired. The author classifies the following as acquired etiological factors: diseases of the neuroendocrine system, infectious diseases, childhood diseases (including rickets), pathology of the nasopharynx, harmfulness, etc. [10]. According to Khoroshilkina F.Ya., Demner L.M. (1987), Betelman A.I. (1965), Pogodin A.A. (1955), Moldovenyask K. (1990), upper respiratory tract pathology contributes to the occurrence and formation of anomalies and deformations of the upper and lower jaws. The root causes that cause impaired nasal breathing and primarily provoke the appearance of oral breathing include: curvature of the nasal membrane, hypertrophy of the inferior turbinates, an increase in the number of cases of adenoid vegetations (in 48.5% of cases) and palatopharyngeal tonsils, as well as other chronic diseases of the upper respiratory tract (60%), which are a mechanical obstacle to nasal breathing. Long-term impairment of nasal breathing contributes to the occurrence of a bad habit of breathing through the mouth, which negatively affects the formation of the entire dental apparatus and leads to narrowing and lengthening of the upper dental arch, deformation of the palate ("Gothic palate»). The

mechanism of deformation formation is caused by the following reasons: during oral breathing, the mouth is always open, as a result of which the pressure of the buccal muscles becomes greater than usual and begins to compress the lateral sections of the dental arches of the upper jaw. A constantly open mouth also leads to a change in the position of the tongue, which normally, when the mouth is closed, contacts the palatine surfaces of the teeth and thereby compensates for the pressure of the buccal muscles on the lateral teeth. When the mouth is open, the tongue stops contacting the teeth and is unable to compensate for the pressure created by the musculature. The lower jaw shifts back due to the increased tone of the geniohyoid, digastric and mylohyoid muscles. As a rule, a combined deformation develops - distal occlusion with deep incisor overlap [4, 11, 12, 13]. Research by A.A. Pogodina (1955), who studied the connection between anomalies of the dental apparatus and chronic diseases of the nose and pharynx using a modified Lozanov rhinopneumometer, found them in 34% of children. In children with normal bite, diseases of the nose and pharynx were found in only 6% of cases. During nasal breathing, negative pressure is created in the oral cavity during inhalation, and uniform positive pressure during exhalation. As a result of this balanced pressure, the jaw develops to a normal shape. During mouth breathing, these conditions are violated and a compressed upper jaw is created. The study by A.A. Pogodina showed that there is no constant, regular connection between pathological bite and impaired nasal breathing functions. The author believes that the mechanical effect of the air stream on jaw deformation is unconfirmed. In her opinion, the development of the most severe forms of bite anomalies in pathological processes in the nose and throat, accompanied by impaired nasal breathing, can be explained by various general pathological changes in the child's body [12]. Lite T. (1955) notes in his work that prolonged breathing is an etiological factor in the occurrence of chronic inflammatory processes in the oral mucosa. The author believes that patients with a typical "adenoid face" have a reduced tone of the upper lip, which becomes flaccid, short-shouldered, and can completely cover the front teeth, which begin to be visualized at rest, due to which an ash-colored smile appears. As a result of the violation of the position of the upper lip and the loss of its function, the flow of saliva from the minor salivary glands located in the lip is lost, as a result of which the effect of cleaning the teeth is reduced. The clear ones are also exposed to negative effects: on the one hand - moistening (from the tongue), on the other (vestibular) - dryness. This wet-dry effect leads to the occurrence of incomplete keratinization of the gums [14]. Ilyina-Markosyan L.V. (1974) found that diseases of early childhood often lead to the formation of dentoalveolar anomalies. In 60% of children with rickets, deformations of the jaw bones and bite anomalies are observed. The disease is based on a disorder of phosphorus-calcium metabolism. Under the influence of the force of the muscles attached to the lower jaw, deformation of the jaw bones occurs. The lower dental arch acquires a trapezoid shape as a result of compaction of the anterior section. The upper dental arch acquires a

saddle shape as a result of pressure of the cheek muscles on the dental arches in the premolar area. Vertical incisor deocclusion is formed. According to the author's observations, most children who suffered from rickets have enlarged tonsils, complicated nasal breathing is noted, which in itself can cause bite anomalies [15]. In order to determine the connection between dental anomalies and impaired nasal breathing, Manna F.F. (1981) together with otolaryngologists examined 2503 children aged 1 to 14 years in children's institutions of the cities of Ufa and Kazan, including 1303 girls and 1200 boys. Formed dentoalveolar anomalies were detected in 1434 children, which is $57.3 \pm 2.1\%$. Of these, 169 ($11.8 \pm 1.8\%$) had anomalies of individual teeth. In 656 ($45.8 \pm 1.3\%$) – anomalies of dental arches and in 609 ($42.4 \pm 2.7\%$) – anomalies of bite. During the examination of ENT organs in the same 2503 children, pathology of the nose and pharynx was detected in 743 ($29.7 \pm 1.9\%$), including hypertrophy of the palatine tonsils in 461 children, chronic rhinitis - in 29, hypertrophy of the inferior turbinates of the nose - in 7, adenoids - in 317, curvature of the nasal septum - in 12, chronic sinusitis - in 13, nasal polyps - in 4 children. is $84.7 \pm 2.7\%$, while in children without pathology of the nose and pharynx, dentofacial anomalies were found only in 691 people, which is $48.1 \pm 1.9\%$ ($p < 0.001$). Based on this, the author came to the conclusion about the causal relationship of dentoalveolar anomalies with impaired nasal breathing [16]. The views of A.A. Pogodina (1958) on the causal relationship of distal, mesial and open bite with impaired nasal breathing are confirmed by the data of the author Mannanova F.F. (1981). In children with ENT pathology and bite anomalies, the most common are distal (51.3%), open (29.1%) and mesial (12.4%) bite. Wagaiyu E.G. and Ashley F.P. (1991) found that obstruction of the upper respiratory tract leads to the development of mouth breathing and, as a consequence, shortening of the upper lip, which in turn causes exposure of the gums, accompanied by a poor level of oral hygiene and gum inflammation. Long-term inflammatory processes and progression of gingivitis lead to bone loss and the formation of bone pockets [24]. Allergic rhinitis and adenotonsillar hypertrophy, which is considered by clinicians Bellanti J.A. et al. (2000), are the main cause of airway obstruction. It is usually associated with various symptoms: lack of nasal airflow, sneezing, itching, runny nose, snoring with the possible occurrence of obstructive sleep apnea syndrome (OSAS) and an increase in respiratory infections, such as ear infections, sinusitis and tonsillitis [25]. , Suntsov V.G., Wagner V.D. (2001) pay special attention to pathologies of the upper respiratory tract as etiological factors in the occurrence of distal bite [26]. Khoroshilkina F.Ya. (2006) believes that constant habitual breathing through the mouth can be caused by various functional and morphological disorders: constant obstruction in the upper respiratory tract in the form of adenoid vegetations, hypertrophy of the palatopharyngeal tonsils, pathological changes in the mucosa; the habit of breathing through the mouth as a result of the consolidation of the reflex, even after the elimination of the obstruction of the upper respiratory tract; reduced function of the muscles

that close the oral cavity, allowing the air stream to pass through the existing gap and leads to the position of the tongue between the dental arches; pronounced sagittal gap between the central incisors, which makes it difficult to close the lips. With such a disorder, the tongue was sometimes wide, the nostrils were narrow, the lips were closed, the contour of the chin was double. The tongue in the oral cavity shifts: the tip is back or forward, the back is located lower. The space between the root of the tongue and the soft palate increases. Such changes lead to the occurrence of anomalies and deformations of the upper and lower jaws and, as a result, the occurrence of sagittal malocclusions [4]. Slavichek R. (2008) attaches great importance to the influence of breathing on the development of physiological occlusion. In his opinion, impaired nasal breathing leads to disproportionate development of the upper and lower jaws. In such cases, the position and function of the tongue are impaired, its influence on the development of the upper jaw decreases. Impaired breathing, as the author notes, also affects posture. Despite the listed facts, as well as the methods of prevention that have been known for a long time, conceptual changes in dentistry in this direction have not occurred [28]. Frequent inflammatory processes in the upper respiratory tract, according to Kutsevlyak V.I. (2013), lead to the habit of breathing through the mouth, while the child's lower jaw shifts distally, the tongue descends to the bottom of the oral cavity, the upper jaw of this alveolar part and the dental arch narrow in the lateral sections and increase their anteroposterior size. narrowing in the lateral areas and lengthening in the frontal area [5]. Gripaudo, E.G. Paolantonio (2016) and colleagues in their article also studied the relationship between breathing through the mouth and bite problems. The authors examined 3017 children using the ROMA index and found that breathing pathology leads to the formation of bite anomalies, in addition, with an increase in the degree of the index, the number of pathologies increases, since obstruction of the upper respiratory tract changes the structure of craniofacial growth [29]. impaired nasal breathing and dentofacial morphology has long been widely studied by Rubin R.M. et al. (1980), and they found that the pattern of craniofacial growth may be influenced by the unbalanced muscle function characteristic of mouth breathing [30]

In the article by Isabel Chung Leng Mucoz (2016) on the topic "Comparison of cephalometric values of upper and lower airway volumes in children with nasal and mouth breathing in the age groups from 6 to 12 years" the author showed that children who breathe through the mouth are characterized by a more posteriorly displaced mandible (SNB) and a greater inclination of the mandibular plane (NS-Go Gn) and occlusal plane (NS-O Pl) than children who breathe through the nose ($P < 0.05$). The group of children who breathe through the mouth also had an elevated position of the hyoid bone, and their nasopharyngeal airspace was significantly smaller than in the group with nasal breathing ($P < 0.001$) [31]. The literature describes many different theories of the mechanism of occurrence of dentoalveolar deformations with complicated breathing, namely:

1) the air stream during mouth breathing rests against the palate and deforms the upper jaw

2) distal bite occurs due to enlarged tonsils and complicated nasal breathing, when the patient tilts the raised head forward to facilitate breathing (M.M. Vankevich)

3) progenia occurs due to constant protrusion of the lower jaw with an enlarged lingual tonsil to facilitate breathing (Herbst, 1908; Isard, 1930);

4) open bite occurs during mouth breathing due to pressure of the tongue on the lower frontal teeth (Misch, 1922);

5) the balance of the muscles of the maxillofacial region is disturbed during mouth breathing (Angel, Körbitz, 1910; Izard), etc.

All theories come down to mechanical compression of the upper jaw. This is evidenced by a wide range of specialized literature indicating major changes in the body with impaired nasal breathing. These changes concern external respiration, blood circulation, digestion, morphological and biological composition of blood, lymph and cerebral circulation, the state of the vascular walls, and higher nervous activity. The pathological condition of the upper respiratory tract has a particularly detrimental effect on the body of a growing child. Now, more than ever, with the advent of the most modern technologies and treatment options, the orthodontist must also recognize and solve respiratory problems. When obstruction of the upper respiratory tract occurs, the body adapts by switching from nasal breathing to oral breathing, while the position of the head changes, the tongue takes an anterior position, and the lower jaw shifts back [32]. All of the above indicates that the mechanism of jaw deformation during oral breathing is explained by the authors, therefore, the role of this factor in the genesis of dentoalveolar anomalies remains not fully understood, but there is no reason to deny the importance of impaired nasal breathing in the etiopathogenesis of dentoalveolar anomalies. Thus, to date, the cause-and-effect relationship between impaired nasal breathing and dentoalveolar deformities has not yet been fully clarified. Not everything has been clarified about the mechanism of occurrence of bite anomalies in pathology of the nose and pharynx - what exactly is the root cause of further morphological changes.

One thing is certain: there is a close pathogenetic connection between dentoalveolar anomalies and impaired nasal breathing, therefore, a prerequisite for successful orthodontic treatment of dentoalveolar deformities in children is the elimination of pathological processes in the nasal cavity and pharynx.

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